

THE ESSENCE AND MAIN DIRECTIONS OF UPBRINGING

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Abstract. *This study provides information about the main content of the formation of education and the main directions of education. Also, information based on historical sources in the formation of educational methods from the discipline of psychology is presented as an example. The importance of modern psychological methods and psychological training in the application of the main methods of education is discussed. The instructive thoughts of our great scholars about education and upbringing are analyzed. The role of spirituality in the formation of education is incomparable.*

Keywords: *Parenting methods, family, spirituality, perfect person, psychological research, worldview formation, upbringing.*

TARBIYANING MAZMUNI VA ASOSIY YO'NALISHLARI

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu tadqiqotda tarbiyani shakllantirishning asosiy ma'zmoni va tarbiyaning asosiy yonalishlari haqida ma'lumotlar keltirib o'tilgan. Shuningdek, psixologiya yo'nalishida tarbiya metodini shakllantirishda tarixiy manbalarga asoslangan ma'lumotlar misol tariqasida aytib o'tiladi. Tarbiyani shakllantiruvchi asosiy metodikalarning qo'llanilishida zamonaviy psixologik metodlarning va psixologik treninglarning ahamiyati haqida muhokama qilinadi. Buyuk allomalarimizning tarbiyaga oid ibratli fikrlari tahlil qilinadi. Tarbiyaning shakllanishida ma'naviyatning o'rni beqiyosdir.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Tarbiya metodlari, oila, ma'naviyat, komil inson, psixologik tadqiqotlar, dunyoqarashni shakllantirish, ta'lim.*

Introduction

In all periods of human history, the issue of education has played an important role in the life of society. Each nation, based on its national values, traditions and historical experience, has created its own system of educating the younger generation. Education is a continuous process that serves the spiritual, mental, physical and aesthetic formation of a person. Great thinkers, scientists, and educators have deeply studied the essence of this process and emphasized the decisive importance of education for human perfection. Education is a social process that ensures the purposeful formation of a person and is carried out on the basis of the needs, goals and ideals of society. The educational process determines a person's behavior, worldview, and the level of adherence to moral standards.

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Abu Nasr Al-Farabi in his work "Thoughts of the People of the Virtuous City" said: "If a person has good qualities in terms of his nature and character, but does not receive education, these qualities will not develop." Abdulla Avloni, on the other hand, deeply expressed the place of education in the life of the nation by saying, "Education is a matter of life and death for us."

This idea shows how important the role of education is in the development of the human personality. The educational process is influenced by many factors, that is, factors. They can be divided into the following groups: The family is the first place of upbringing for a person. A child learns love, care, and decency first of all in the family. The personal example of parents, their behavioral culture, and moral values have a great influence on the spiritual world of the child. As the hadith says: "Every child is born with nature, and it is his parents who make him a Jew, a Christian, or a pagan." This hadith clearly expresses the main role of the family in upbringing.

Schools, colleges, lyceums, and higher educational institutions constitute the next stage of the educational process. At this stage, the child develops qualities such as hard work, responsibility, friendship, and loyalty to the homeland, and begins to develop as a person. The success of pedagogical activity largely depends on the personality of the teacher, his professional skills and human qualities. The cultural environment in society, the media, the Internet, the circle of friends, social networks also directly affect the upbringing of young people. If the social environment is in the spirit of healthy ideas, national values and goodness, the spiritual maturity of the individual is formed. Otherwise, these factors can have a negative impact. The education system is closely related to the historical traditions, customs, and religious beliefs of the people.

Imam Ghazali wrote: "Not educating a young child is tantamount to corrupting him."

Therefore, it is important to form feelings such as honesty, patience, modesty, respect for parents, and love for the Motherland in the hearts of children based on religious values. Natural factors - climate, health status, and physical capabilities - also have a certain impact on human upbringing. Therefore, the educational process should be carried out taking into account the individual characteristics of the person. The formation of upbringing is a continuous process that covers all periods of human life. Upbringing methods are a set of methods used in the upbringing process and are of great importance in the formation of a person. The most effective methods include: Conversation and explanation method. Through an educational conversation, moral views and spiritual values are formed in children. The method of encouragement and punishment. If this method is used correctly and appropriately, responsibility and discipline are strengthened in a person. Personal example. If the educator himself is not an example, his words will not have any effect. Confucius said: "To give a good upbringing, first educate yourself." Upbringing through a team. Upbringing carried out within a group or team develops social activity and cooperation in a person. Upbringing through labor. Labor educates a person, instills patience, perseverance, and responsibility. In historical sources, the issue of upbringing has been studied in depth by many scientists. Spiritual maturity is the degree to which a person has achieved moral, spiritual and intellectual maturity. Education is the basis of this process. A spiritually mature person brings about positive changes in society and becomes an example for others. Through education, a person not only gains knowledge, but also learns to understand himself and to interact correctly with others. In today's era of globalization, new approaches to the educational process are required.

Therefore, the modern education system is being improved in the following areas: the formation of information culture; strengthening patriotism based on national ideas; strengthening family and school cooperation; and the use of person-oriented pedagogical methods. Modern pedagogy adopts a competency-based approach as the main model of the educational process. In this approach, practical skills, values, and relationships are at the center, not knowledge.

According to the competency-based approach, the result of education is measured by a person's ability to successfully function in life. The content, goals, and stages of education are one of the important socio-cultural processes that have been pondering humanity for centuries.

Nowadays, education is considered not only a means of conveying traditional moral values, but also a strategic process that ensures the creative, intellectual, and spiritual development of the individual. Modern pedagogical research studies education as a dynamic system that forms the human personality. In this system, biological, psychological, social, cultural and spiritual factors interact. The effectiveness of education is determined by its correct organization in practice, adaptation of methods to conditions and age characteristics. The practical application of methods in the formation of the worldview of young people - combining theoretical knowledge with life experience, helps to strengthen spiritual values in everyday activities. Therefore, the importance of educational methods in expanding the worldview of young people is incomparable.

Because education and upbringing bring a person to adulthood not only as an educated person, but also as a spiritually perfect, morally pure, socially active person. The harmonious application of educational methods on scientific, national-spiritual foundations brings the younger generation to the level of a fully mature person. This, in turn, is the most important factor in the development of the country. The educational environment means all external influences in the conditions in which a person lives. From this perspective, it can be concluded that through upbringing, a child can be adapted to the social conditions in which he lives. They consider the role of the social environment to be a decisive factor. Then, not everything that surrounds the child is considered a real environment in his development. For each child, a unique and completely individual situation of development arises, which we call the immediate environment. At the same time, it implies relative independence. The microenvironment is also part of the social environment and consists of family, school, friends, peers, loved ones and similar elements. There are both positive and negative phenomena in the environment surrounding the child. The personality is formed not only by absorbing the influence of the environment, but also by resisting it. The conditions of development cannot affect the formation of the personality without depending on how the child himself interacts with them and how he is formed in these conditions. Psychological research shows that if a child is respected by his peers, if he is entrusted with responsible tasks, this helps him develop confidence, activity and communication skills, or, conversely, people and similar elements. The environment surrounding the child includes both positive and negative phenomena.

Conclusion

The personality is formed not only by absorbing the influence of the environment, but also by resisting it. The conditions of development cannot affect the formation of the personality without taking into account how the child himself reacts to them and how he is formed in these conditions.

The environment surrounding the child becomes a means of upbringing as a result of labor and language. In this, it is necessary to take into account that the influence of the environment arises spontaneously. Therefore, it is necessary to allow education and upbringing to take a leading place in human development.

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